

CULTIVATION OF THE MEDICINAL PLANT DOG ROSE (SHIPOVNIK OBYKNOVENNYY)-(ROZA CANINA L.) AND ITS EFFECT ON HUMAN HEALTH

Rasulov Ilhom Makhmudovich

Associate professor

Samarkand state university named after Sharof Rashidov

Institute of Agrobiotechnologies and Food Safety

Department of Agrochemistry and Plant Protection

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Abstract. *The adoption of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2020 PD-4670 "On measures for the protection, cultivation, processing and rational use of available resources of medicinal plants growing in the wild". Now how to implement systematic work on medicinal plants fully demonstrated that it is necessary. That is, to create a favorable environment for the further development of the cultivation and processing of medicinal plants, to unify many areas towards a single goal with the continued rational use of the gifts of our mother nature.*

Keywords: *C, B2, P, E, K, carotene, sugar, fat, organic acids, flavanoids, pectin, atherosclerosis, avitaminosis, dermatitis, scabies, itching, eczema, psoriasis.*

Introduction. Medicinal dog rose can be found in the lower and middle mountain ranges of Tashkent, Fergana, Samarkand, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Jizzakh regions, on the banks of rivers and streams, in gardens, in walnut and juniper groves. Dog roses are propagated only from sexless, 5-15 cm long stem cuttings.

Root cuttings are prepared at the end of the season, at the beginning of November. The cuttings are cut to a length of 5-15 cm and buried in sand at a depth of 0.5 meters until April. In the spring, the cuttings are dug up and planted in film greenhouses covered with a white cloth (to protect from direct sunlight) without a fogging device. Soil fertilized with rotted manure (at the rate of 2 buckets per 1 m²) and thoroughly crushed, leveled, and covered with river sand 15 cm thick is an optimal place for planting a pen. Cuttings are planted obliquely at a depth of 2.5-3.5 cm. It is watered with a watering can 4 times a day, every three hours. There should be drinking water taken from a ditch or slightly cooled.

The amount of watering is reduced to 1 time (in the morning). At the beginning of September, the covering fabric is removed from the lower part of the greenhouse, leaving only the upper side. It is watered by sprinkling once a week.

In early October, the fabric above the greenhouse is completely removed, watering is stopped. Seedlings reach a height of 50-80 cm, form several stems, industrial plantations are established. Unimproved seedlings are planted separately at a distance of 20 cm from each other, with a row spacing of 60 cm. In autumn, the land set aside for sowing is plowed to a depth of 25-30 cm. It is leveled and ground in the spring. 40x40 cm in size and 50 cm in depth, nests for planting seedlings are dug by hand or with a hole digger. A bucket of rotted manure mixed with phosphorus (1:5) is placed in each of these pits. Fertilizer is mixed into the soil at the bottom of the pit.

Watered up to 10 times in the first year. It should also be taken into account that the root network may be damaged when the cultivator is deeply sunk or driven deep by hand. In the place where the root is damaged, the fungus increases, it interferes with the development of the plant bush, and the yield of the bush decreases. The resulting root buds should be removed slowly. If its root network is well developed, it is planted instead of dead seedlings. If the roots are not well developed, they are cut, and if the agrotechnics recommended for separate land are strictly followed until they are well developed, the varieties will bear fruit in the second year after planting. Seedlings bear fruit in the 3rd-4th year and later.

Dog rose stems grow up to 5 years, then they are replaced by new growth. Old stems are periodically trimmed. Or every 6-7 years, all the stems are removed from the field. A rejuvenated plant will flower and bear fruit after a year. The main disease of Dog rose is powdery mildew on leaves, young stems and branches. To combat it, the plant is dusted with sulfur powder. The most common pests in the garden are aphids and spider mites.

When working with Dog rose, it is necessary to wear thick gloves. Only workers with special skills and knowledge should be involved in processing using pesticides and toxic chemicals.

Dog rose is one of the gifts of nature in protecting human health and preventing diseases. Traditional healers of the past and present have mentioned dozens of healing properties of Dog rose in their books.

Dog rose contains vitamins C, B-2, P, E, K, which are extremely necessary for human health. It is also extremely rich in carotene, sugar, fat, organic acids, flavonoids, pectin, mineral salts and other substances. The fruit contains potassium, iron, manganese, phosphorus, calcium, and magnesium from mineral salts.

According to the great scientist and physician Abu Ali ibn Sina, all types of namatak have cleansing and diluting properties. It kills earworms, is beneficial for ringing and buzzing in the ears, toothache. If applied to the forehead, wild thyme relieves headaches. All its types unclog nasal passages. It is also useful for swellings in the throat and tonsils.

Dog rose flowers, fruits, seeds, leaves and roots have been widely used in folk medicine since ancient times. Tinctures and decoctions made from the fruit are used in folk medicine to treat pulmonary tuberculosis, rubella, typhus, inflammation of the gall bladder, gastrointestinal, kidney, and bladder diseases.

Its fruit gives energy to the body, improves metabolism, and its nuts are used to drive urine in the treatment of kidney and urinary tract diseases. Tincture and decoction prepared from the root of the plant are used among the people for stomach and liver diseases, and the powder is used as a cure for wounds.

Dog rose decoction, i.e. juice, is recommended in folk medicine for the treatment of many diseases. In order to get juice, 10-15 of its fruits are washed and boiled for ten minutes in a secret pot and eaten.

To prepare namatak tincture, put four to five namatak fruits in a half-liter thermos, pour boiling water over it, leave it overnight, and then strain it in the morning. The infusion is drunk three times a day twenty minutes before meals. This tincture gives energy to the whole body, increases its endurance, relieves cough, treats inflammation of the digestive tract, relieves liver pain.

It is beneficial to gargle with it several times when the mouth has a cold. In the case of uterine bleeding in women, it is useful to boil namata for a long time and drink its juice. Dog rose decoction is considered the best remedy in the treatment of scabies. If it is given to the patient as a tea, the blood will be cleansed and the wound will get rid of it, and it is better to apply its juice to the wound to heal faster.

For patients with cold menstruation and low blood pressure, namatak tincture replaces the most healing tea. If people who have colds in their hands, feet, and other organs in severe cold drink its decoction often, it will heat up the body and expel toxic substances into the urine. It is recommended to wash the eyes often with a decoction of namatak when the eyes become watery due to colds, itches or itches.

Even when the bladder and kidneys are suffering from a cold, if the patient is bathed in hot water with a decoction of namatak, it will be cured. You can also wash the top of the bladder several times in the boil. When the muscles catch a cold, in the case of sciatica, applying the decoction of namatak to the painful, painful areas relieves the pain. This decoction is also useful in treating small red, watery rashes on children's bodies due to colds. For this, the child is bathed in a decoction or vaccinated with it several times during the day. Dog rose whets children's appetite and gives them energy.

This boon gradually repels obesity, because it cleanses and washes the bowels, and accelerates small ablutions. People who are weak and have dry skin will benefit if they drink its leaves instead of tea. Put two tablespoons of namatak fruit in a thermos filled with boiling water, let it rest overnight, and then strain it. If you drink 100 ml of it two or three times a day before meals, you will be cured of anemia, impotence, atherosclerosis, kidney and liver diseases, colds, vitamin deficiency.

300 ml of crushed neem leaves in one tablespoon. it is infused in boiling water for two to three hours in a closed container and filtered. If you drink this with two tablespoons of honey two to three times before meals, it will help in healing wounds that are difficult to heal. If two grams of dried namatak fruit are crushed and eaten per day, it helps to prolong human life and preserve sexual power.

Dog rose tincture and decoction are not suitable for people with hot mood, because it has a negative effect on the pancreas of such people. Also, namatak decoction is not useful for diseases that appear due to high fever, such as high blood pressure, diabetes, liver diseases, hemorrhoids, iron deficiency. Since the drug C in Dog rose erodes the enamel layer of the tooth, after eating it, the mouth must be rinsed with warm water. In modern medicine, tinctures, extract and wet fruit juice, as well as pills and kholosis are prepared from namatak fruit. These drugs are used for the treatment of avitaminosis and atherosclerosis. Carotolin drug is useful in the treatment of skin diseases such as non-healing wounds, dermatitis, scabies, itching, eczema, psoriasis. Vitamin and polyvitamin teas are made from the fruits of all types of Dog rose, and in the food industry, vitamin-rich mixture, candies and confectionery products are made.

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